

	Electron distribution	dates		Pole side	observation time [s]	Median of the brightness (std) [kR]			Median of inversed <E> (std) [keV]			Median of alt of the VER max (std) [km]		
		start	end			PE	ME	OE	PE	ME	OE	PE	ME	OE
PJ6	Monoenergetic distribution	2017-05-19 01:01:05	2017-05-19 10:39:48	N	10166	115 (98)	206 (249)	18 (103)	82 (31)	70 (9)	54 (22)	231 (94)	259 (14)	281 (196)
				S	12995	21 (240)	724 (398)	21 (128)	74 (49)	93 (16)	63 (24)	259 (256)	222 (15)	270 (199)
	Kappa distribution			N	10166	115 (98)	206 (249)	18 (103)	99 (106)	60 (27)	31 (27)	190 (13)	197(4)	213 (11)
				S	12995	21 (240)	724 (398)	21 (128)	97 (149)	150 (71)	46 (32)	190 (20)	190 (7)	197 (11)
PJ11	Monoenergetic distribution	2018-02-07 10:14:14	2018-02-07 18:49:52	N	8267	55 (120)	143 (238)	11 (82)	86 (44)	64 (9)	52 (22)	231 (119)	270 (53)	292 (237)
				S	15426	27 (210)	321 (347)	22 (93)	62 (37)	75 (10)	62 (22)	270 (200)	250 (13)	270 (196)
	Kappa distribution			N	8267	55 (120)	143 (238)	11 (82)	117 (169)	44 (21)	28 (19)	190 (19)	197 (7)	213 (10)
				S	15426	27 (210)	321 (347)	22 (93)	59 (97)	81 (38)	44 (25)	197 (16)	197 (5)	197 (10)
PJ20	Monoenergetic distribution	2019-05-29 06:35:04	2019-05-29 13:06:28	N	4931	30 (81)	175 (210)	20 (57)	73 (30)	71 (17)	51 (23)	250 (152)	259 (73)	292 (234)
				S	15146	24 (113)	328 (246)	25 (107)	64 (27)	73 (14)	60 (23)	270 (201)	250 (26)	270 (213)
	Kappa distribution			N	4931	30 (81)	175 (210)	20 (57)	70 (82)	65 (40)	23 (26)	197 (14)	197 (11)	213 (11)
				S	15146	24 (113)	328 (246)	25 (107)	55 (52)	73 (50)	39 (36)	197 (7)	197 (12)	197 (11)
PJ32	Monoenergetic distribution	2021-02-21 16:23:18	2021-02-21 22:38:33	N	2768	34 (188)	309 (529)	16 (83)	72 (37)	74 (23)	50 (22)	259 (191)	250 (51)	292 (235)
				S	14384	31 (191)	575 (448)	20 (120)	65 (30)	88 (18)	53 (21)	259 (167)	240 (18)	281 (216)
	Kappa distribution			N	2768	34 (188)	309 (529)	16 (83)	86 (95)	76 (81)	23 (18)	190 (15)	197 (9)	213 (10)
				S	14384	31 (191)	575 (448)	20 (120)	58 (94)	128 (78)	27 (19)	197 (14)	190 (8)	213 (10)
PJ42	Monoenergetic distribution	2022-05-23 01:25:56	2022-05-23 07:13:52	N	2560	21 (32)	71 (78)	17 (46)	65 (27)	58 (20)	47 (24)	259 (216)	270 (164)	292 (243)
				S	13187	36 (160)	304 (192)	44 (136)	66 (27)	64 (11)	62 (21)	259 (203)	270 (48)	270 (167)
	Kappa distribution			N	2560	21 (32)	71 (78)	17 (46)	50 (46)	32 (24)	27 (24)	197 (12)	205 (10)	213 (11)
				S	13187	36 (160)	304 (192)	44 (136)	60 (54)	45 (21)	43 (41)	197 (6)	197 (12)	197 (11)
PJ43	Monoenergetic distribution	2022-07-05 08:30:14	2022-07-05 14:15:32	N	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
				S	13813	136 (468)	314 (235)	56 (197)	76 (40)	68 (15)	59 (25)	250 (186)	259 (17)	270 (214)
	Kappa distribution			N	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
				S	13813	136 (468)	314 (235)	56 (197)	91 (138)	60 (56)	36 (40)	190 (16)	197 (7)	197 (12)